

Exploring Market Segmentation and Digital Strategies in Morocco: A Path to Competitive Advantage using big data and artificial intelligence tools.

Transition Marketing : Vers un Marketing Prédicatif avec les Big Data et l'Intelligence Artificielle.

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Résumé :

Notre étude en deux parties, essentiellement qualitative, a commencé par une enquête exploratoire via un questionnaire en ligne, générant 100 profils dont une dizaine ont été sélectionnés pour une analyse principale plus approfondie à l'aide d'entretiens semi-directif. Nous avons ainsi étudié les stratégies de segmentation et de ciblage du marché au Maroc, en mettant l'accent sur le marketing traditionnel, le marketing prédictif, la présence numérique, le Big Data et l'intelligence artificielle. Le marketing traditionnel se concentre principalement sur l'interaction hors ligne entre l'entreprise et le consommateur, tandis que le marketing prédictif utilise largement la présence numérique et le Big Data pour comprendre en profondeur les besoins des consommateurs, permettant à l'entreprise de se positionner sur des marchés de niche. Notre modèle illustre les interactions entre la présence numérique, l'utilisation du Big Data, la capacité à répondre aux besoins des consommateurs, et l'application de l'intelligence artificielle.

Nous avons observé que 80 % des entreprises n'exploitaient pas le Big Data et que seulement 40 % avaient adopté une approche stratégique axée sur le numérique. De plus, 20 % des entreprises se positionnaient en tant que "niche". Selon nous, ces entreprises bénéficient d'un avantage concurrentiel en utilisant l'intelligence artificielle pour innover et proposer des offres uniques et personnalisées aux consommateurs en temps réel, surpassant ainsi la concurrence et favorisant la satisfaction et la fidélisation des clients.

Mots clés : Marketing digital ; Marketing prédictif ; BD ; IA ; Maroc.

Abstract:

Our two-part, essentially qualitative study began with an exploratory survey via an online questionnaire, generating 100 profiles, of which around ten were selected for a more in-depth main analysis using semi-structured interviews. We studied market segmentation and targeting strategies in Morocco, focusing on traditional marketing, predictive marketing, digital presence, Big Data and artificial intelligence. Traditional marketing focuses primarily on the offline interaction between the company and the consumer, while predictive marketing makes extensive use of digital presence and Big Data to gain an in-depth understanding of consumer needs, enabling the company to position itself in niche markets. Our model illustrates the interactions between digital presence, the use of Big Data, the ability to respond to consumer needs, and the application of Artificial Intelligence.

We found that 80% of companies were not exploiting Big Data and that only 40% had adopted a strategic approach based on digital. What's more, 20% of companies were positioning themselves as 'niche' players. In our view, these companies gain a competitive advantage by using artificial intelligence to innovate and deliver unique, personalised offers to consumers in real time, outperforming the competition and driving customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Keywords: Digital Marketing ; Predictive Marketing ; BD ; AI ; Morocco.

Introduction:

The overall aims of our study were to gain an understanding of the market segmentation and targeting strategies being adopted in Morocco, as well as the effectiveness of their strategic choices in relation to any digital tools at their disposal. We wished to identify the degree to which they were making the transition from traditional to digital and predictive marketing, including the use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. We explored perceptions, feelings and experiences regarding:

- Technology and how technology influenced their choices
- Digital marketing
- Predictive marketing
- Big Data
- Artificial Intelligence
- The emergence of digital strategies in Morocco

As our research has evolved, and with reference to the theoretical themes outlined in later sections of this paper, we have begun to develop a hypothesis about the key factors at play as businesses embrace and participate in the shift from traditional marketing to digital, predictive marketing, and ultimately maximising the leverage of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. This hypothesis raised a central issue: how can Moroccan businesses take full advantage of digital tools, such as Big Data and Artificial Intelligence, to move from a traditional marketing approach to a predictive and personalised digital strategy, while overcoming the challenges associated with their adoption and implementation?

Following on from this problematic, our article unfolds as follows: We begin by outlining the methodology adopted and the justification for our choice of research, detailing the size of the business sector and the professional experience of the respondents, accompanied by a table summarising the profiles of the participants. We will then describe the process followed in this study, and the limitations encountered. The results will then be presented, focusing on the details provided by each respondent, according to the size of the company and their professional experience. Finally, the conclusion will highlight the practices identified through the results obtained. The appendices and bibliography will complete the article to provide a comprehensive overview of our research.

In this research, we adopted a mixed methodology combining exploratory quantitative analysis to identify target profiles, followed by in-depth qualitative analysis including semi-structured interviews with market experts to explore segmentation strategies and digital approaches to marketing in Morocco.

The significance of predictive technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) is the focus of numerous studies in Morocco. A pertinent article on this topic is by Mrs. LAHRACHE R. and BEKKAOUI A. (2024), titled "L'impact de l'intelligence artificielle sur la prise de décision," published in the Revue Internationale des Sciences de Gestion, Volume 7, Issue 3, pages 660-678. This research explores the influence of AI on decision-making processes, highlighting its growing relevance in various sectors.

To fully understand the impact of digital strategies, it is important to examine the key factors that determine a company's success in the modern digital environment.

Figure A1: when to invest in a predictive strategy

*** Strategic: Digital First (Fully integrated, maximum exposure across all relevant digital platforms)
 ** Tactical: e-commerce plus some degree of digital and social media platforms
 * Transactional: e-commerce only

Figure A1

Made by us. (2024).

We identified some key elements:

1. The degree of, investment in, and commitment to Internet Presence. Namely, whether companies take a strategic, tactical or transactional approach.
2. The capacity to identify consumer needs at a granular level via Big Data – enabling strategic, individuated segmentation.
3. The possibilities offered by Artificial Intelligence to maximise opportunities to customise their products, services and/or ideas to meet those newly revealed consumer needs - in Real Time, when the first 2 parameters are met.

If the enterprise limits its digital presence to e-commerce only, and elects not to use Big Data, then it may only satisfy the requirements of a **Limited Product Line**.

If the enterprise invests heavily to create a digital presence but fails to leverage Big Data, it could be a one-way street. The consumer is able to find them but they have no insight into the preferences of the consumer resulting in **Wasted Opportunities**.

If the enterprise invests heavily in Big Data but fails to create a strong digital presence, this could be another kind of one-way street. They have insight into the preferences of their potential consumers but are invisible to them thus the **Target is Missed**.

If the enterprise creates both a strong digital presence and leverages insight into the preferences of its consumers, it enters the **NICHE** quadrant: a two-way, mutual connection between enterprise and consumer.

The benefits of Artificial Intelligence only arrive when the enterprise is already Niche. At that point, the enterprise can leverage **AI** to innovate and provide unique, individual offers to consumers in **Real Time**, outdoing the competition and creating customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Disruptive innovation, a concept introduced by Clayton Christensen in 1997, refers to innovations that fundamentally alter markets and business sectors by introducing simpler, more practical and often more affordable products or services. In the context of digital strategies, this theory is particularly relevant. In Morocco, the growing adoption of digital technologies has introduced disruptive changes in market segmentation and marketing practices.

Traditional businesses that have failed to embrace these innovations find themselves threatened by new, often more agile, businesses that use digital technologies to target market segments more precisely and effectively. For example, the use of artificial intelligence and big data enables these new companies to predict consumer behaviour and adapt their offers in real time, which represents a significant competitive advantage.

Based on Disruptive Innovation Theory, it is possible to analyse how digital strategies are transforming market segments in Morocco, encouraging the emergence of new players capable of responding more effectively to consumer needs. This transformation is particularly visible in sectors such as retail, where online platforms and mobile technologies have revolutionised the way consumers shop.

1. Methodology and Rationale

As our subject was somewhat technical and requiring a certain professional expertise, and to ensure the applicability and generalisability of our study, we made the decision to implement a “*Purposeful Sampling Strategy*”, adopting a criterion-based approach:

*“Purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources (Patton, 2002). This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that **are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest** (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011). In addition to knowledge and experience, Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) note the importance of availability and **willingness to participate, and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an articulate, expressive, and reflective manner.**” (Our emphasis). (Brookfield, S. D., & Preskill, S. (2012). *Discussion as a way of teaching: Tools and techniques for democratic classrooms*. John Wiley & Sons).*

The collection of data had two parts. Part One took the form of an online survey and Part Two was a detailed qualitative interview. At Phase One, our aim was to identify individuals with an adequate level of knowledge and understanding of our subject so that, at the second, qualitative stage, our conclusions would have the qualities of rigour, applicability and generalisability. We also wished to ensure the seriousness with which the respondents took our subject and their willingness and ability to share their knowledge and experience.

We commenced by using Linked-In to identify Marketing Managers and Specialists in Morocco. We generated 100 click-throughs to the survey.

From the 100 who clicked through, 24 either completed or partially completed the questionnaire. Through this process, we were able to rule out 76 people who had shown their lack of *willingness to participate fully*; leaving us with 24 active participants. Further refinement, according to our criteria, ruled out an additional 9 participants who demonstrated only surface knowledge. We were able to identify them by the way they filled in the survey.

Our criterion-based process had screened out the unsuitable Respondents, leaving us with 13 Professionals who met our criteria. They had demonstrated:

- Knowledge of the Subject, answering most or all items in a congruent manner
- Professional Experience, relating to the concepts and ideas presented
- A Willingness to Participate, including giving their attention to detailed responses
- The ability to communicate and articulate, including adding open ended responses.

In Qualitative Research validity is mainly established by demonstrating that the sample cohort is representative of the wider population it is said to represent. To this end, we further refined the sample cohort to a size of 10. This further selection of respondents created a representative sample in terms of Experience, Company Size and Sector. The final 10 respondents presented this comprehensive profile.

1.1. Size of Enterprise Sector Professional Experience:

Proceeding with the selected cohort, we conducted an interview of about thirty minutes by video call or in-person. This second, and major, phase of our study, we deemed to justify the use of an Interpretivist Approach. The aim was not so much to produce absolute objective evidence, which would have been more easily garnered via quantitative means, as to gather the subjective views, perceptions and interpretations. To get a sense of their levels of acceptance and uptake of the new approaches and technologies. To build a picture of where their areas of resistance might lie in terms of the personal and social context of the Marketing Function in modern day Morocco. And how their organisational contexts presented, according to their world view.

The research aims and methodology were viewed as congruent with Denscombe’s definition of interpretivism, namely that:

- Social reality is subjective
- Humans react to the knowledge that they are being studied
- Humans react to the knowledge produced by being studied
- It is not possible to gain absolute objective knowledge about social phenomena

1.2. Table: Profile of Respondents:

Size of Enterprise	Sector	Professional Experience
More than 2000 staff	Financial Services	6+ years
50 - 200 staff	E-commerce	3-5 years
50 - 200 staff	E-commerce	1-2 years
50 - 200 staff	Telecommunications	3-5 years
50 - 200 staff	Telecommunications	1-2 years
Fewer than 20 staff	Marketing Agency	6+ years
Fewer than 20 staff	Marketing Agency	3-5 years
Fewer than 20 staff	Marketing Agency	1-2 years
Fewer than 20 staff	Telecommunications	3-5 years
Fewer than 20 staff	Telecommunications	1-2 years

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Denscombe’s approach seemed to fit our study so long as we were aware of its limitation; if we were able to focus our research more specifically on the subjective experiences and understanding of Marketing Professionals in relation to these key Marketing themes. Taking on board Denscombe’s warning that the Interpretivist Approach can otherwise lack rigour, we had confidence that our careful and rigorous use of our Purposeful Sampling Strategy, adopting a criterion-based approach, would mitigate any weakness in that regard.

2. Process Followed

We created a root question and shared it with each respondent in advance of our interview, so they had time to reflect and prepare. During the interview, depending on their response to the

root question, we had a bank of questions as potential resources. Not every question was required and questions were not always asked in same order – we were flexible and open, according to the respondent's presentation.

Our interview questions were open-ended to allow the respondent the freedom to answer without influence or direction so that the results are reflective and transparent. Our use of supplementary questions was aimed at ensuring the validity, comprehensiveness and generalisability of our findings without compromising the qualitative principles of the research.

3. Limitations of the Research

While it was hoped that the findings would give some illumination to our understanding of the digital landscape in Morocco, it is important to acknowledge that this was a modest, small-scale study with consequent limitations as to the generalisability and transferability of the findings. While we endeavoured to identify the most representative group possible, by means of Purposeful Sampling, using a criterion approach, it still remains up for debate the extent to which our respondents could be deemed representative of marketers in Morocco.

4. Findings:

4.1. Respondent R1 (Mid-Size Company, Telecom, 6 years' experience)

R1 shared that her team were all on board and committed to the digital journey. Their main justification for using digital were sales, finding new prospects and customer service. They tried to keep the “normal channels” updated and they have a limited budget for paid advertising. Her main concerns were that they did not always have a clear strategy and understanding of how to make the best of digital possibilities.

4.2. Respondent R2 (Large Company, Financial Services, 5 years' experience)

R2 demonstrated a lot of excitement about the digital journey and especially about how “the exploitation of data is a source of implementation of effective actions and planning”. They have a dedicated data team and, while they have not yet arrived at their destination, he shared his feeling that “Predictive hyper-personalization can offer marketers a lover's advantage with typical profiles, we can or products better suited to our customers.”

We would categorise their Internet Presence as highly strategic including how they target activity and budget spend “SEO is optimised throughout the year, and Facebook, to spread more of our content, the rest is mainly put forward during campaign periods.” They subscribe to several services on News Tracker and actively take action to implement and change course as quickly as possible.

4.3. Respondent R3 (Large Company, Telecoms, 4 years’ experience)

R3 shared a little bit of frustration on his part as he had to spend a lot of time and energy convincing colleagues and directors about the benefits of a more modern approach. Their main focus for digital was Sales, lead generation and brand awareness. They had perhaps made small mistakes in the past, for example investing in Instagram and not yielding much Return-On-Investment. Their preferred channels were now Website, LinkedIn and Facebook.

R3 did not want to discuss Predictive Marketing – he was mainly focused on getting the basic digital piece right. Similarly, he showed no interest in Big Data or AI at this time.

4.4. Respondent R4 (Mid-Size, Company, Financial Services, 1 years’ experience).

R4 was very frank and forthcoming about how their focus in current times was more about getting internal processes right while keeping the Marketing Function ticking over. They are placing their attention these day on digitising all their internal systems in order to be more efficient and to be able to respond to customer needs. In terms of marketing, they prioritise customer service, sales and brand awareness. In the past, they did not really know how to differentiate and benefit from the various channels available. Currently their advertising spend includes Website, LinkedIn and Influencers. But he felt that “Data is hard to track and it is difficult to justify the budget spend.” In terms of the potential offered by hyper-personalisation, he did not see how his company could deliver or benefit from that. His overall attitude was about getting the basics right.

4.5. Respondent R5 (Small Company, e-commerce, 1 years’ experience)

R5 worked in a small family-owned business which sells artisan products online and also in their physical premises where they have a shop, a café and a workshop. She was mainly focused

on creating content for their website, Instagram and Pinterest. Her budget is very limited and there is low management buy in. But she was confident that, once the owners saw the tangible benefits of digital presence, they would be more responsive. Given the nature of the business, they already customise products “for us, customisation is standard” and they do this directly with and for their customers. She did not perceive a need for business such as theirs to spend money on Big Data or Predictive Marketing.

4.6. Respondent R6 (Small Company, e-commerce, 1 years’ experience)

R6 was one of 3 people working in Marketing for a small artisan business, selling furniture 100% online to the domestic market. The only “customisation” they offered was a choice of colour on a small section of the product range. Given the small size of the company, and being 100% online, their investment in having 3 Marketing Professionals was a positive indication of their commitment to Digital.

Their main focus was sales and attracting people to their website. They also used Facebook and Instagram to publicise their offer. They had experimented with using Influencers but did not yet have a plan for how to get the maximum benefit from that investment.

4.7. Respondent R7 (Mid-Size Company, Boutique Marketing, 5 years’ experience)

R7 worked for a company whose main business was selling digital shopper insights and analytics. In terms of his company’s Marketing Practice, their focus was on increasing brand awareness, generating leads and sales. They had a big database of email addresses, collected via various campaigns, and this was their first priority; followed by Instagram and Website. In terms of advertising spend, they used a lot of SEO, automatically updating, to publicise and connect with Marketers and Business Analysts via Instagram, LinkedIn and Glassdoor, the latter with a view to capturing the attention of potential employees. They already use Predictive Marketing tools and are becoming more adept at translating the data into actionable insights.

4.8. Respondent R8 (Mid-Size Company, Telecoms, 3 years’ experience)

R8 was responsible for marketing and communication at this mid-size Telecoms business. Their main focus for digital was Sales, prospects and customer service. Their preferred channels were

Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn as that is where the business felt customer alignment. On the other hand, they used paid advertising on Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram and had actually got really good results from Instagram. A lack of aligned thinking and business planning probably meant that they missed some opportunities. Also not taking the time to reflect and investigate results. Everyone was busy already and keen to move on to the next project or initiative.

Their current use of Predictive Marketing was low. It was more a case of having a good online presence and good services on offer. He could agree with a future involving Predictive, Big Data and AI but was not able to articulate how his business would leverage those tools.

4.9. Respondent R9 (Small Company, Boutique Marketing, 8 years' experience)

R9 was the CEO of a boutique marketing and consumer insights company. Their main focus in terms of digital were lead generation, directing traffic to the website and also customer service. They invested in advertising/marketing on Google Business Finder, LinkedIn and SEO for the website. They also some paid positioning of YouTube from time to time. He felt they got the best returns from LinkedIn and the website. "Given the nature of our business, professional to professional, that makes sense. We help other marketers to find us on LinkedIn and then they investigate us on our website."

4.10. Respondent R10 (Small Company, Boutique Marketing, 1 years' experience)

R10 worked in a company within a small tight-knit marketing function where everyone seems to be aligned and on-message with the digital journey: "Any marketing actions that we do have a digital aspect (relay, event promotions, Influencer actions, etc.)" He has learned a lot from his colleagues and also been sponsored to take training courses in the Fundamentals of Digital Marketing, Google Ads for Mobile, and an expert SEO course via LinkedIn.

Their top three reasons for using digital were customer service, sales and attracting good employees. They also use digital to direct traffic to the website, to connect with potential customers and to increase brand awareness. They are highly client focussed: "everything depends on the objectives of our clients".

Their Internet Presence was high and they took advantage of 9 channels, with email being their number one method to reach out to existing and potential clients and Google Business Finder being second.

While they use Predictive Marketing to a small extent, they do not really have the skills to know what to do with the data and a lack of strategic vision. There is also some fear of change and failure and spending money on data that they would not be able to track.

In terms of marketing practice, we would conclude that most companies have focussed on building their internet presence; some with a clear strategic intent but most coming from a tactical or transactional point of view. In some cases, they seem to use every channel at their disposal while not being clear as to why and what each channel can offer them or how to prioritise investment in time and budget. While none of our respondents mentioned Predictive SEO, overall, there was a reasonable understanding and uptake of SEO and digital advertising. There is significant scope to increase the use and understanding of Big Data and how to leverage Hyper Personalisation. There may also be misunderstandings about access to, and the costs of, Big Data. Only 1 company in our study was availing themselves of one such service (News Tracker).

Figure A2: when to invest in a predictive strategy

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Figure A2 attempts to plot each of the 10 companies in terms of the key themes already outlined. 8 of the 10 don't make it over the 50% mark for their use of data and hyper personalisation.

Only 4 companies seemed to take a digital-first, strategic approach to their online presence. The two enterprises using Big Data were also adopting a strategic approach to digital presence, placing them in the niche quadrant, with high potential to leverage the benefits of AI. However, while many companies in Morocco have only embarked on the early stages of the digital journey, the excitement, commitment and enthusiasm of our respondents gives us reason to hope for a bright future.

The study focused on understanding the market segmentation and targeting strategies in Morocco, along with the adoption of digital tools such as Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. We found that companies in Morocco vary in their digital maturity, with some taking a strategic approach while others have a more tactical or transactional mindset.

The findings revealed that companies prioritize sales, lead generation, and customer service as their main objectives for digital marketing. While there is a general awareness of the importance of digital presence and utilization of channels like websites, social media, and paid advertising, there is room for improvement in terms of clear strategies and understanding of the potential benefits.

Regarding the adoption of advanced technologies, such as Big Data and Artificial Intelligence, the majority of companies have yet to fully leverage their capabilities. Only a few companies in our study were actively using Big Data, and even fewer were exploring the potential of predictive marketing and hyper-personalization. There is a need for increased awareness, understanding, and investment in these areas to unlock their benefits.

The study also highlighted the importance of a strong digital presence combined with insights from Big Data to establish a two-way connection between enterprises and consumers. Companies that successfully integrate these elements can position themselves in a niche quadrant, where they can leverage Artificial Intelligence to provide unique, personalized offers in real-time, fostering customer satisfaction and loyalty.

It is important to note that this study had limitations in terms of sample size and representativeness. However, the enthusiasm and commitment demonstrated by the respondents indicate a positive outlook for the future of digital marketing in Morocco. With further

education, strategic planning, and investment, Moroccan companies can harness the power of digital tools to drive their marketing efforts and stay competitive in the evolving landscape.

5. Discussion, Implications and Research Perspectives

In this study of market segmentation and digital strategies in Morocco, the results revealed a notable diversity in the digital maturity of companies, reflecting the stages of transition described in the literature. While some companies are adopting strategic approaches, others remain in more tactical or transactional phases, highlighting limited adoption of advanced technologies such as Big Data and artificial intelligence. This observation is consistent with trends in emerging markets, where the exploitation of these technologies remains modest despite a growing awareness of their benefits. The managerial implications of these findings suggest that to maximise their competitiveness, Moroccan companies need to intensify the integration of these technologies into a coherent and comprehensive digital strategy. Scientifically, this research provides an in-depth understanding of the digital maturity of companies in this specific context, highlighting challenges in terms of awareness and training. The study calls for increased investment in digital technologies and enhanced strategic planning to fully exploit the tools available, with prospects including greater personalisation and more sophisticated use of Big Data.

Conclusion:

In terms of marketing practices, we can conclude that most companies have focused on developing their online presence, with some doing so with a clear strategic intent, while the majority approach it from a tactical or transactional perspective. In some cases, they appear to utilize all available channels without a clear understanding of why they are doing so, what each channel can offer, or how to prioritize investments in terms of time and budget. Although none of the respondents mentioned predictive SEO, the understanding and use of SEO and digital advertising are generally reasonable.

There is significant room for improvement in the use and understanding of Big Data and how to leverage hyper-personalization. There may also be misunderstandings regarding access to and the cost of Big Data. Only one company in our study utilized one of these services (News Tracker).

Figure A2 attempts to represent each of the 10 companies based on the key themes already described. Eight out of the 10 companies do not exceed the 50% mark in their use of data and hyper-personalization. Only four companies seem to adopt a strategic and digital approach to their online presence. The two companies using Big Data also adopted a strategic approach to their digital presence, placing them in the niche quadrant, with strong potential to leverage the benefits of AI.

However, while many companies in Morocco are still in the early stages of the digital journey, the excitement, engagement, and enthusiasm of our respondents give us hope for a bright future.

The study aimed to understand market segmentation and targeting strategies in Morocco, as well as the adoption of digital tools such as Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. We found that companies in Morocco vary in their digital maturity, with some adopting a strategic approach while others maintain a more tactical or transactional mindset.

The results revealed that companies prioritize sales, lead generation, and customer service as their primary objectives in digital marketing. While companies are generally aware of the importance of a digital presence and the use of channels such as websites, social media, and paid advertising, progress remains to be made in terms of clear strategies and understanding potential benefits.

Regarding the adoption of advanced technologies such as Big Data and Artificial Intelligence, the majority of companies have not yet fully tapped into their capabilities. Only a few companies in our study actively used Big Data, and even fewer explored the potential of predictive marketing and hyper-personalization. There is a need to increase awareness, understanding, and investment in these areas to fully harness their benefits.

The study also highlighted the importance of a strong digital presence combined with insights from Big Data to establish a two-way connection between companies and consumers. Companies that successfully integrate these elements can position themselves in a niche quadrant, where they can leverage Artificial Intelligence to offer unique and personalized real-time offers, fostering customer satisfaction and loyalty.

It is important to note that this study has limitations in terms of sample size and representativeness. However, the enthusiasm and engagement demonstrated by the respondents

indicate a positive outlook for the future of digital marketing in Morocco. With more training, strategic planning, and investment, Moroccan companies can harness the power of digital tools to enhance their marketing efforts and remain competitive in an ever-evolving landscape.

ANNEXES

SEMI-DIRECTIVE INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR THE ATTENTION OF MANAGERS AND MARKETING PROFESSIONALS IN MOROCCO.

The study seeks to measure the effectiveness of segmentation and targeting strategies adopted in Morocco, as well as the strategic choices made by marketing managers, both according to the tools and skills, which are at their disposal. To do this, we are developing an approach to verify the effectiveness of intuitive targeting strategies and the transition to digital.

From the first phase of the research, ie the on-line questionnaire, we have identified 13 Marketing Professionals who demonstrate a good knowledge and interest in our subject. Phase One was an opportunity to exclude 8 participants with only surface knowledge from the second, qualitative phase – we were able to identify them by the way they filled in the survey and, in most cases, by failing to complete.

The 13 respondents for Phase 2 indicated a seriousness about the topic. All 13 demonstrated their commitment to the subject, answering most or all items and offering additional information and comments.

The following key findings demonstrate a good working knowledge and that the group for Phase 2 are authentic marketing professionals in the Moroccan context:

- 77% have undertaken some form of digital marketing training in the last 3 years. (Item 1)
- 85% work in enterprises where digital plays a major role in the development of their customer targeting strategies. (Item 2)
- 85% feel that Managers are on board with the Digital approach. (Item 3)
- Their online presence is more than simply transactional – ranging from tactical to strategic across 6 key areas – Sales, Brand Awareness, Developing Prospects, Directing People to the Website and even to Attract New Employees. (Item 4)

The data from the on-line survey relating to these 4 Items is attached as Appendix A. Proceeding with the selected group, we will use their answers to the on-line survey as a basis to delve further and deeper into their experience concerning the marketing strategies of consumer choice in Morocco. We will conduct an interview of about thirty minutes by video call or in-person. We will cover 8 topics that received interesting responses in the online survey. The questions in our interview are open to give the respondent the margin to answer without influence or direction so that the results are more reflective and transparent.

1. How their digital choices/strategies are supported or limited by the available technology
2. Future plans and aspirations including being more strategic, budget spend and staff training
3. This group all use predictive strategies but to different degrees. How they feel about using

predictive strategies and their experience so far.

4. How they feel and experience the challenges of predictive marketing.
5. How they view Big Data and potential advantages.
6. How they feel about Machine Learning
7. Their views and feelings around the possibilities for hyper-personalized segmentation.
8. How they feel about the emergence of digital strategies in Morocco.

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